

Comparison of physical models for bifacial PV power estimation

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ABSTRACT

There is a growing tendency towards the application of bifacial photovoltaic (BFPV) systems all around the world, and it is predicted that they will soon take the largest share of the market. For a BFPV system, accurate estimation of power, as the main output, plays an important role as it is a critical need for trader/forecast providers and operations and maintenance companies to detect deviations from expected output. Typically, in the industry practice in the best case scenario, an effective irradiance is calculated, which combines both the global (front) tilted irradiance (GTI) and the rear tilted irradiance (RTI) into a single input parameter. Considering this point, a data-driven model has been developed here to obtain a parameter called dynamic bifacial power gain (DBPG). Adding DBPG to monofacial photovoltaic (MFPV) power output results in determination of BFPV power production. Therefore, the novel proposed data driven model (called DBPG model) is able to estimate the rear side production separately, which helps to analyze and diagnose a BFPV system better. A BFPV plant with horizontal single-axis tracking (HSAT) in Eurac Research, Bolzano, Italy, is considered as the case-study and model development is done for both black and white ground conditions. The results have confirmed much higher accuracy of the DBPG model compared to PVlib, as a tool that uses the effective irradiance. Normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) values of power estimation by PVlib are 2.99% and 4.59% for black and white ground conditions, while these are reduced to 1.14% and 2.02%, respectively, by taking advantage of the DBPG model. Moreover, excluding the near shadows conditions from the computation, using PVlib leads to 3.26% and 8.25% error in total yield estimation for ground with black over a period of almost 3 months and white surfaces over a period of almost 17 months. The corresponding values for DBPG model are much lower, i.e., 0.58% and 1.98%.

1. Introduction

With the value of 447 GW, the annual growth rate of photovoltaic (PV) installed capacity in 2023 experienced 87% growth compared to the previous year, i.e., 239 GW [1]. It occupies 78% of the added capacity of the whole renewables in 2023, where the corresponding values for wind, hydro, and biomass energies were 117 GW, 7 GW, and 4 GW, respectively (1 GW also for others) [1].

In addition to the installed capacity, the market share of different PV types is also changing rapidly, with the favor of BFPV technologies [2–4]. It comes from several advantages BFPV have, including the higher power production per area [5–7]. Moreover, it has shown that among MFPV and BFPV with fixed-tilted (FT), single-axis tracking (SAT), and dual-axis tracking (DAT) strategies, using BFPV with SAT is accompanied by the lowest levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for

majority of potential PV sites on the Earth [8]. Based on the 15th International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic (ITRPV) [9], there is an equal share in market for MFPV and BFPV technologies in 2024. The contribution of BFPV will increase to ~70% in 2030.

Accurate estimation of power is important for various purposes, including fault detection by operations and maintenance companies [10–12] and trading/forecast provision [13–15]. A widely adopted approach for power estimation of PV systems is using PVlib [16]. Identical approach to MFPV is employed for performance simulation of a BFPV by PVlib, in which as a simplifying assumption, an effective irradiance is defined to take rear tilted irradiance (RTI) and global tilted irradiance (GTI) at the same time [16]. As an alternative way, the historical data has been employed to provide models which could have higher accuracy.

The historical data has been utilized in some research works to develop new semi-empirical models. For instance, Bouchakour et al.

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Nomenclature	
<i>Symbols</i>	
<i>DBPG</i>	Dynamic bifacial power gain (–)
<i>P</i>	Power (W)
G_E	Effective irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>GTI</i>	Global (front) tilted irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>RTI</i>	Rear tilted irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>PR</i>	Performance ratio (–)
<i>T</i>	Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
<i>NRMSE</i>	Normalized root mean square error (–)
<i>NMAE</i>	Normalized mean absolute error (–)
<i>NMBE</i>	Normalized mean bias error (–)
<i>SS</i>	Selection score (–)
<i>Y</i>	Yield (kWh/kW_p)
<i>Period</i>	The investigated time period (s)
<i>t</i>	Time (s)
<i>DNI</i>	Direct normal irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>GHI</i>	Global horizontal irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>DHI</i>	Direct horizontal irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>MBE</i>	Mean bias error (–)
K_{cs}	Clear-sky index (–)
<i>RMSE</i>	Root mean square error (–)
<i>Greek symbols</i>	
φ	Bifaciality
γ	The temperature coefficient of maximum power ($\%/^{\circ}C$)
η	Efficiency (–)
<i>Subscripts</i>	
<i>rear</i>	Rear side
<i>amb</i>	Ambient
<i>n</i>	Nominal
<i>cell</i>	Solar cell
<i>STC</i>	Standard Test Conditions ($G = 1000 W/m^2$; $T = 25^{\circ}C$; $AM = 1.5$)
<i>Temp_corr</i>	Temperature corrected
<i>i</i>	Counter (for thermal model)
<i>j</i>	Counter (for electrical model)
<i>min</i>	The minimum
<i>P</i>	Peak
<i>REAL</i>	The real operating condition
<i>Superscripts</i>	
<i>est</i>	Estimated
<i>front</i>	Front side
<i>MF</i>	Monofacial PV
<i>BF</i>	Bifacial PV
<i>model</i>	Model
<i>PVlib</i>	PVlib
<i>DDM</i>	Data-driven model
<i>cs</i>	Clear-sky condition
<i>rear</i>	Rear side
<i>Abbreviations</i>	
<i>PV</i>	Photovoltaic
<i>BFPV</i>	Bifacial PV
<i>MFPV</i>	Monofacial PV
<i>SAT</i>	Single-axis tracking
<i>HSAT</i>	Horizontal single-axis tracking
<i>DAT</i>	Dual-axis tracking
<i>LCOE</i>	Levelized cost of electricity
<i>ITRPV</i>	The International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic
<i>FT</i>	Fixed-tilt
<i>ANN</i>	Artificial neural network
<i>RSM</i>	Response surface methodology
<i>CEC</i>	California energy commission
<i>NOCT</i>	The nominal operating cell temperature
<i>NMOT</i>	The nominal module operating temperature
<i>SAPM</i>	Sanida array performance model
<i>AM</i>	Air mass
<i>ITRPV</i>	The international technology roadmap for photovoltaic
<i>SVM</i>	Support vector machine

[17] took advantage of the historical data to find current and voltage of a BFPV system. The input parameters covered a variety of parameters, including the effective irradiance, the thermal voltage, the empirical diode factor, and so on. Their case included three strings with FT configuration in Terrassa, Spain. The semi-empirical model was compared with the analytical model originally presented in [18]. Despite the good accuracy of the semi-empirical model, the analytical model showed a better estimation. Similarly, Mannino et al. [19] evaluated different semi-empirical models to estimate current and voltage of a FT BFPV system. They compared estimation of Sandia Array Performance Model (SAPM) [20] with the model developed by Cristaldi et al. [21] and Faifer et al. [22]. Their investigated case was in Catania, Italy. Some modifications to them had been also presented. The model had the inputs like current (in voltage model), effective irradiance, temperature, and GTI. They found that irradiance could be replaced with the current in the voltage model, while changing the fitting approach led to changing the results.

Furthermore, Yuan et al. [23] considered double diode model for a BFPV module and modified the parameter estimation way using an evolutionary algorithm called four-state Jaya. The model got a number of parameters, such as the effective irradiance as the input. A good agreement was observed for the investigated case-study, which had FT configuration.

In another group of studies, data-driven models have been developed using historical data. Artificial neural network (ANN) has been the most

popular tool for this purpose. As an example, ANN was utilized by Ghenai et al. [24] to determine power of a FT BFPV rooftop system in Sharjah, the UAE as the case-study. The training data came from simulation by PVSyst software program, in which some simplifying assumptions, including considering effective irradiance has been used. Moreover, Yunqiao and Yan [25] applied bidirectional gated recurrent unit network for power estimation of a BFPV unit. Model development was done for a power station with FT in Jiuquan, China. Support Vector Machine (SVM) has been the other employed data-driven model. SVM was utilized by May et al. [26] for output power estimation of a BFPV system with FT. Module characteristics, in addition to the weather conditions (including effective irradiance) was required to run the model as the inputs.

Historical data has been also used for estimation of yield. The investigation done by Castillo-Aguilella and Hauser [27] could be given as an example. In that study, various FT conditions with different angles had been considered for Tucson, the USA, and an equation for determination of the bifacial energy gain was given. The equation was a function of tilt angle, albedo, and height. The same work also was performed by Ghenai et al. [28], in which PVSyst data had been given as the input to find the impact of albedo, tilt angle, and height on yield and bifacial energy gain. The response surface methodology (RSM) had been employed with 27 series of data as the input. Moreover, Radwan et al. [29] used RSM and PVSyst to find the impact of height, tilt angle, spacing, and albedo on annual energy generation. The results indicated

the great impact of tilt angle, spacing, and albedo.

In addition, using historical data, some correlations have been found between modeling data and measurement values. For example, Rodriguez-Pastor et al. [30] simulated performance of a BFPV system in greenhouse application with view factor approach and one-dimensional thermal modeling. Their model considered soiling vegetation. Having developed their model, they introduced some correlations between modeling and experimental data. The equations were found for actual temperature as a function of modeled value, and for the real and simulated energy. A second-degree polynomial as a function of RTI had been also fitted to the energy data. In addition, Alam et al. [31,32] analyzed the data for a FT BFPV system in Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, the UK. They examined various albedo conditions. Then, correlations were found for total power output and total irradiance, bifacial energy gain and irradiance gain, and irradiance gain and clearness index. A moderately high correlation between the bifacial energy gain and irradiance gain was found. The fitted line had a slope of 0.61 and an intercept of 1.37%.

Literature review has shown that despite the valuable performed studies, there is still the gap in the availability of physical data-driven models for power estimation of a BFPV by which the contribution of the rear side to the power production could be determined separately. Therefore, as the novelty, this work provides such model, which helps to analyze and diagnose a BFPV system better. In the proposed approach of this study for modeling BFPV power, a parameter called Dynamic Bifacial Power Gain (DBPG) is defined as the contribution of the rear side. Then, DBPG is found as a function of RTI using the historical data. The model is developed for an HSAT BFPV plant owned and managed by Eurac Research, Bolzano. Two conditions for albedo are considered with black and white colored ground (low and high albedo, respectively). The model was then benchmarked with PVlib. Comparison of DBPG model with PVlib is done in details by considering power production profiles for sample clear-sky and cloudy days, as well as the yield.

2. Data-driven power estimation methodology

The proposed approach of this investigation considers BFPV power (P^{BF}) as:

$$P^{BF} = P^{MF} + P_n^{BF,front} DBPG \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) is schematically shown in Fig. 1, as well. In this equation P^{MF} denotes produced power of a MFPV with the identical specifications to the front side of BFPV when ambient temperature and G_{TI} are the same as BFPV. $DBPG$ is the Dynamic Bifacial Power Gain. $DBPG$ indicates how much more power BFPV is able to produce compared to MFPV at the same solar and ambient conditions in the terms of $P_n^{BF,front} = P_n^{MF}$. Based on Eq. (1) $DBPG$ could be defined in the form of:

$$DBPG = \frac{P^{BF} - P^{MF}}{P_n^{BF,front}} \quad (2)$$

$DBPG$ should not be confused with the bifaciality factor, which is usually indicated by φ [33]. φ is the ratio between performance (power, current, or voltage) of rear and front sides when temperature is 25 °C and the investigated side is receiving 1000 W/m² in the absence of irradiance on the other side [34]. Mostly, the ratio of power values is expressed as the bifaciality coefficient.

A data-driven model is developed here to determine $DBPG$. The proposed data-driven model (DDM), which is called DBPG model, calculates $DBPG$ from Eq. (3):

$$DBPG^{(est\ model)_{DDM}} = PR_{rear} \times \left(\frac{RTI}{1000} \right) \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) provides a correlation between RTI and $DBPG$ with a coefficient. The coefficient could be interpreted as the performance ratio of the rear side (PR_{rear}).

In the real operating condition, where BFPV modules are working, usually, there is no installed MFPV with the same specifications as BFPV. As a result, P^{MF} has to be obtained from modelling and in this investigation, PVlib is utilized for this purpose. Different combinations of thermal and electrical models in PVlib have been examined and the most accurate of them is chosen based on the relative error matrix presented in section 4.1.

Eq. (1) could be updated by indicating the ways to find P^{MF} and $DBPG$ in this investigation:

$$P^{BF(est\ model)_{DDM}} = P^{MF(est\ model)_{PVlib}} + P_n^{BF,front} DBPG^{(est\ model)_{DDM}} \quad (4)$$

Actually, $DBPG$ approach models the residuals (the estimation errors), i.e., it is a second order model. Accuracy of the $DBPG$ model is evaluated by comparing its estimation with PVlib (Eq. (5)). PVlib approach to determine BFPV power output is the same as MFPV but using effective irradiance (G_E) as the input [16]:

$$P^{BF(est\ model)_{PVlib}} = P^{MF(est\ model)_{PVlib}}(G_E, T_{amb}) \quad (5)$$

In which T_{amb} is the ambient temperature.

In order to remove any existing outliers, after removing the nights, the data has been filtered by a statistical filter based on the temperature corrected performance ratio ($PR_{Temp_corr}^*$):

$$PR_{Temp_corr}^* = \frac{\frac{P^{BF}}{P_n^{BF,front}}}{(1 + \gamma(T_{cell} - T_{STC})) \left(\frac{G_{TI}}{1000} + \varphi \frac{RTI}{1000} \right)} \quad (6)$$

where T_{cell} and γ denote cell temperature and the temperature coefficient of maximum power. The superscript ‘*’ is added to PR in Eq. (6) to emphasize BFPV power has been normalized using nominal power of

Fig. 1. The graphical representation of the DBPG model.

Fig. 2. The investigated BFPV system (a) Front side; (b) Rear side.

front ($P_n^{BF, front}$) and T_{STC} is the Standard Test Condition (STC) temperature of 25 °C (The irradiance and air mass (AM) for STC are also 1000 W/m² and 1.5, respectively). PR is widely recognized as a key metric for evaluating the performance of PV systems. PR is a dimensionless parameter that describes the relationship between the received irradiance and the energy output of the PV system. Due to the nearly linear relationship between power and irradiance over a broad range of irradiance, this metric can effectively identify and exclude unrealistic power-irradiance pairs caused by issues such as sensor shading, misalignment, or other anomalies. PR has a high dependency on temperature. Therefore, it is recommended to adjust PR for temperature effects. This adjustment helps to perform the filtering process more accurately [35].

3. Case-study

A plant owned and managed by Eurac Research, Bolzano, Italy, is considered as the case-study (Fig. 2). The plant has 2 BFPV systems, each composed of 2x12 modules. BFPV systems are equipped with horizontal single axis tracking. From the two systems one of them is chosen for investigation. The information about the considered case-study has been summarized in Table 1. “Lab measurements” in this table refers to testing modules by the facilities in Eurac Research for the indoor tests, where STC had been imposed. Moreover, the places of measurement devices have been shown in Fig. 3. Pyranometers have been utilized to record GTI and RTI (One for each). Temperature is also measured in three points for each string: 1. Close to the edge, 2. Close to the center, and 3. In the middle. In addition, the data reported by the weather station adjacent to the plant have been used to assess real operating conditions, including air temperature and wind velocity.

For an initial period the ground was kept homogeneous between the 2 portion of the field. Then, white painting was applied to one portion of the plant:

Table 1
Introducing the considered case-study.

Parameter	Value/Condition
Number of PV modules (rows × PV modules per row) per system	2 × 12
Tracker axis tilt	0
Tracker axis azimuth	18°
Range for tilt change	±55°
BFPV technology	Heterojunction technology (HJT)
Average nominal front capacity of the used modules, lab measurements ($P_n^{BF, Front}$)	374.01 W
Average bifaciality, lab measurements (ϕ)	0.903

- **Black ground:** From July to October 2022,
- **White ground:** From October 2022 to February 2024.

DBPG model for BFPV power estimation is developed for each of the indicated conditions separately. In addition, the limits for $PR_{Temp_corr}^*$ filter are chosen 0.586 and 0.971 for the black ground, and 0.571 and 0.987 for the white ground. In that way, the tails of the distribution for $PR_{Temp_corr}^*$, as the filtering criterion, has been removed, which are mainly the points with the near shadow. The near shadow comes from a metal fence and a tree located in the surrounding of the string.

4. Results and discussion

In this section, we discuss the results related to: choosing the most accurate combination of the thermal and electrical models to define the “PVlib model” used as a reference (4.1); evaluating the value of the backside performance ratio (PR_{rear}) to be used in our “DBPG model” (4.2); and comparing the accuracies of DBPG model and that of PVlib (4.3). The comparison is made by evaluating the errors in the estimation of power and yield.

4.1. The most accurate combination of thermal and electrical models

In PVlib, several thermal and electrical models are available, the first is used to retrieve from real operating conditions the cell temperature and the second uses the modelled cell temperature and the irradiance measurements to estimate the PV generation. We found the most accurate combination among the available alternatives, for the used case study. For this purpose, the normalized root mean square error between measurements and PV power output estimated by the i^{th} thermal and j^{th} electrical models ($NRMSE_{ij}$) was calculated.

NRMSE is a widely-used index in accuracy evaluation of renewable energy systems performance estimation tools. As a big advantage, NRMSE gives more weight to larger errors due to the squaring of differences, making it effective in applications like PV power output estimation where significant deviations are undesirable (Due to load management issues).

Since there is no change in the modules when the ground was white compared to the time with black ground, NRMSE was computed for the whole period. To better highlight the results of this analysis, we construct the selection matrix (Fig. 4) using the skill score of (SS_{ij}) with respect to the best performing thermal/electrical model combination (with minimal NRMSE):

$$SS_{ij} = 1 - \frac{NRMSE_{ij}}{NRMSE_{min}} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. The place of measurement devices.

	CEC	Desoto	Pvsyst	PVWatts	SAPM
SAPM	-11.59	-11.59	-6.90	-17.63	-3.78
Faiman (NMOT) model	-21.91	-21.91	-17.23	-27.20	-14.11
Faiman model augmented with a radiative loss term	-13.10	-13.10	-8.72	-19.40	-5.79
Fuentes	-10.71	-10.71	-6.02	-16.62	-2.90
Ross model (NOCT)	-8.31	-8.31	-3.32	-13.85	0.00

Fig. 4. The selection matrix to find the best combination of electrical (columns) and thermal (rows) models in PVlib. Bold data indicates the best combination.

The lower is SS_y the lower is the model accuracy.

Fig. 4 shows that, in our case, the most accurate PV power output estimation is obtained by the thermal Ross model (known as the Nominal Operating Cell (NOCT)) model [36] and the electrical Sandia Array Performance Model (SAPM) [20]. The better accuracy of NOCT compared to other more complex thermal models is probably due to the knowledge of the exact NOCT value of the modules, measured by the manufacturer and reported in the data sheet. In contrast, the semi-empirical parameters for other thermal models are not available in the datasheet and they have to be estimated. On the other hand, the simplest electrical model, PVWatts [37], was found to have the lowest accuracy. California Energy Commission (CEC) [38] and De Soto [39] models showed similar accuracy.

In the paper, we call “PVlib model” the most accurate combination of electrical and thermal models (SAPM and NOCT) reported above.

4.2. Performance ratio of the rear side of the plant

To assess the value of the performance ratio of the rear side of the plant (PR_{rear}) we split the production data in two sets: 70% of the filtered data is utilized for retrieving PR_{rear} , while the remaining 30% (randomly selected) for testing the model. PR_{rear} was retrieved by the linear fitting of the dynamic bifacial power gain (DBPG) against the normalized rear tilted irradiance ($\frac{RTI}{1000}$). Fig. 5a and b show the scatter plots for the black ground and white ground cases. The slope of the linear fitting represents the PR_{rear} values. As expected, changing the color of the ground from black to white results in a wider range of RTI variability. The highest value of RTI when the soil is black is around 120 W/m², while for the white soil it is about 350 W/m² (Approximately 3 times larger).

Moreover, Fig. 5a and b show that for each case, there is an area with accumulation of the points and a wide range of DBPG values

Fig. 5. Finding the values of PR_{rear} : (a) Black ground; (b) White ground.

corresponding to a specific RTI. The area is marked by a double arrow in Fig. 5a. For Fig. 5b it is the part indicated by the left double arrow (RTI below 150 W/m^2). The issue comes from the non-uniformity of RTI throughout the center to edges. It is worth noting that RTI is measured only at the center of the string, and this “edge-effect” [34] cannot be quantified.

On the one hand, there are points with DBPG close to zero at not zero RTI conditions. Such points appear in the clear-sky condition just before the shading of the PV string. In that period, a part of the surrounding ground is covered by the near shadow thus the modules closer to the shadowed ground receive lower RTI compared to the others. This leads to a module current mismatch. If GTI is low and the shadow is big, the drop in bifacial power output gets significant, which results in close to zero DBPG. At the same time, there may also be a small part of the front side of the string covered by a nearby shadow. The performance drop due to this shaded part is so small that it has not been detected by the statistical filter, but it actually leads to a reduction in the measured power output (P^{BF} in Eq. (2)). However, the front-side PVlib model (which uses the irradiance measured at the plane of the modules) cannot account for this reduction, providing an overestimation of the front-side generation (P^{MF} in Eq. (2)). For these reasons, DBPG can be near zero (or even negative) under not-zero RTI conditions. The analysis can be confirmed by data clustering to extract the points with the described condition. Clustering works based on application of the clear-sky index (K_{cs}) to detect the clear-sky condition:

$$K_{cs} = \frac{GTI}{GTI_{cs}} \quad (8)$$

Here, the Ineichen/Perez model [40,41] in combination with the isotropic sky diffuse model [42,43] is utilized to obtain GTI_{cs} .

Fig. 6a shows the clustered data found by applying the limits for K_{cs} , GTI , and the near shadow time. The chosen limits are K_{cs} greater than 0.6, GTI smaller than 550 W/m^2 , and hours between 13 and 15 (The limits have been determined by trial and error). In Fig. 6b the values of sun elevation angles for the clustered data are also introduced using the color bar. Like Fig. 6a, Fig. 6b is in agreement with the analysis since the shadow is big at low sun elevation angles.

As the extra information for Fig. 6b, Fig. 6c is provided, which separates the cluster points based on the season. Fig. 6c demonstrates that the low sun elevation angles are mostly seen in fall and winter.

On the other hand, under clear-sky condition with high GTI and low to moderate sun elevation angles, the tilt angle of the modules increases to maximize the irradiance capture. The tilted PV modules block most of the sun’s rays from reaching the ground area they cover. However, there is a higher RTI than center of the string for the modules on the edge of it since they could receive reflection from the surrounding, as well. This results in a higher effective rear irradiance for the whole string than RTI in the center of that (The measured value used to draw the scatter plot), and a bigger DBPG.

Data clustering could be also employed in this case for confirmation. The points describing the clear-sky and high GTI condition are identified

by applying the limits for K_{cs} and GTI . The chosen limits are K_{cs} greater than 0.60 and GTI higher than 550 W/m^2 (found by trial and error). In addition, since the negative effect of near shadow on surrounding might cancel out the indicated positive effect or even become dominant, the hours with this possibility are excluded. Therefore, for hour, the limit of not between 13 and 15 is selected. The isolated points based on the three indicated criteria (K_{cs} , GTI , and hour) are introduced in Fig. 7a. Furthermore, Fig. 7b presents the distribution of sun elevation angle for the cluster using a colorbar. Fig. 7a and b are in agreement with the analysis. The seasonal distribution of cluster points is also displayed in Fig. 7c.

The discussed points could be also seen by plotting hourly profiles of GTI , RTI , and $DBPG$, for a sampled clear-sky and overcast day (Fig. 8a and b). In order to get a clearer picture, GTI is normalized by 2000 W/m^2 (instead of the usual normalization of 1000 W/m^2). In the clear-sky day during not shadowed conditions (from 9:00 to 15:30), $DBPG$ follows RTI shape (Fig. 8a). However, when it gets close to the shadow conditions (before 9:00 and after 15:30), $DBPG$ experiences a sudden drop to near-zero values. In contrast, in the case of the cloudy day, the $DBPG$ follows the RTI profile for almost the entire day, as no nearby shadows occur. Fig. 8a and b also show that at low RTI (under cloudy conditions or in the morning and afternoon) the backside performance (ratio of $DBPG$ to $RTI/1000$) can be even higher than under clear sky conditions around noon, probably due to lower module temperature and more uniform backside irradiation. Therefore, at low rear-side irradiation ($RTI < 150 \text{ W/m}^2$) we can observe both very high and very low $DBPG$, resulting in the wide scattered distribution observed in Fig. 5a and b. In contrast, under high tilted rear irradiation (clear sky conditions around noon and white ground), the $DBPG$ is clearly proportional to the received rear irradiation, with a fine distribution independent of RTI values.

On average, the backside performance at low RTI is lower than high RTI , which explains why with black soil the PR_{rear} is 0.2544 while with white soil it reaches 0.4642 (82.5% higher). At low RTI , the irradiance effect plays an important role and the drop in the backside performance due to that becomes considerable.

Therefore, $DBPG$, and consequently, total power output in higher albedo condition, is higher not only for the higher collected reflected irradiance but also for the higher rear side performance.

However, it is worth noting that the observed behavior of module performance is closely related to the near shadows affecting the system and cannot be generalized.

As a matter of fact, from the above considerations, we expect an exactly opposite behavior under shadow-free conditions. Higher performance at low RTI and lower performance at high RTI and thus higher performance (PR_{rear}) with black ground than with white ground.

4.3. Accuracy evaluation compared to PVlib

The ability of $DBPG$ model to estimate power and yield is evaluated with PVlib in parts 4.3.1 and 4.3.2, respectively.

Fig. 6. Application of the clustering technique to the scatter plot of Fig. 5b to find the reason for having data with DBPG close to zero and RTI of non-zero (negative edge effect); (a) The cluster detection; (b) Showing the sun elevation angle for the cluster points by the color bar; (c) Seasonal distribution of the cluster points.

4.3.1. Power output estimation accuracy

The accuracy evaluation of the DBPG model is carried out in two ways:

- Comparing the error for the test data, as seen in Fig. 9 (30% of the filtered data is kept for test).
- Comparing the estimation for a sample clear-sky day and a sample overcast day (Fig. 10). Data from these sample days were not included in the training set.

Fig. 9a and c shows that for both black and white ground conditions PVlib model provides an overestimation (positive Mean Bias Error (MBE)). The same can also be seen in the daily profiles from Fig. 10a–d.

This difference in MBE between the two albedo conditions is still visible in the performance of DBPG model, but the overestimation is about eight times less than that of PVlib. Fig. 9b and d show that the DBPG model leads to a significant decrease in Normalized Mean Bias Error (NMBE) compared with the PVlib model: from 2.64% to 0.34% for the black ground, and from 3.86% to 0.84% for the white ground. Moreover, the accuracy of the PV power estimation has been improved

Fig. 7. Application of the clustering technique to the scatter plot of Fig. 5b to find the reason for having the data with higher DBPG than the linear fit for that (positive impact of edge effect); (a) The cluster detection; (b) Showing the sun elevation angle for the cluster points by the color bar; (c) Seasonal distribution of the cluster points.

considerably. NRMSE decreases from 2.99% to 1.14% when ground was black and from 4.59% and 2.02% when ground was white.

The classical approach only takes into account the different nominal efficiency of the rear and front (As PVlib does):

$$\varphi = \frac{\eta_{STC}^{rear}}{\eta_{STC}^{front}} \quad (9)$$

However, DBPG approach considers the plant rear performance in

real operating conditions:

$$PR_{rear} = \frac{\eta_{REAL}^{rear}}{\eta_{STC}^{rear}} \quad (10)$$

This is why the DBPG approach outperforms the PVlib model.

The improved accuracy of the DBPG model power estimation could also be observed through the daily profiles for the sample clear-sky and overcast days (Fig. 10). For both sampling days and the two ground

Fig. 8. Checking profiles of GTI, RTI, and DBPG to see the near shadow period effect; (a) Sample clear sky day; (b) Sample overcast day.

Fig. 9. Scatter plots of power outputs (observation vs estimation) and accuracy of power estimation models (a) PVlib, black ground; (b) DBPG model, black ground; (c) PVlib, white ground; (d) DBPG model, white ground.

Fig. 10. Comparing hourly profiles of power estimated by PVlib and DBPG model with the observed data for sample days (a) Clear sky, black ground; (b) Overcast, black ground; (c) Clear sky, white ground; (d) Overcast, white ground.

conditions, the DBPG model provides a power estimate much closer to the observations.

The non-negligible bias and lower accuracy of PVlib can be partially attributed to the value of the bifaciality factor. To calculate the effective irradiance we used the average value of the bifaciality factor of the string modules (0.903), while the MBE and consequently RMSE could be reduced by using lowest bifaciality factor (0.899) thus taking into account the back current mismatch. During the lab measurements, the nominal power of the rear and front sides were determined, and the bifaciality factor was obtained for each module as the ratio of them. Then, the average and minimum of the values for the string modules were found, which are 0.903 and 0.899, respectively. An accuracy comparison between considering the average value and lowest value of

Table 2

Comparison of the accuracy of the PVlib model when the average and lowest modules' bifaciality values are used to compute the effective irradiance. The better result is shown bold.

The ground color	Considered bifaciality	NRMSE	NMAE	NMBE
Black	Average (0.903)	0.0299	0.0264	0.0264
	The lowest (0.899)	0.0233	0.0190	0.0185
White	Average (0.903)	0.0459	0.0386	0.0386
	The lowest (0.899)	0.0424	0.0345	0.0343

the bifaciality factor in the PVlib modeling is presented in Table 2 for both black and white ground conditions.

However, even considering the lowest bifaciality factor PVlib bias and RMSE still remain much higher than the one obtained by DBPG model.

The improved performance of DBPG model can be further explained by considering that PVlib does not take into account degradation, and current mismatch due to the “edge effect” since it uses only effective irradiance and air temperature as the inputs. In contrast, DBPG model was trained on real PV generation data, and thus embeds all these effects. Most important, DBPG model considers the RTI dependent bifacial power gain and thus account for bifaciality factor time variability in real operating conditions [30]. Finally, it accounts also for the difference rear-side performance according to the ground albedo. However, it should be noted that the accuracy achieved in the higher albedo conditions (white ground) is for both models much lower than that in the lower albedo (black ground). This is because the errors in the estimation of the PV back-side performance has an higher impact on the model accuracy in white ground conditions.

4.3.2. Yield

In this section, we present the accuracy of the models in terms of yield. Yield is defined as:

$$Y(\text{period}) = \frac{\sum_{t \in \text{period}} P(t)}{P_n} \tag{11}$$

where $P(t)$ and P_n are the produced power at the time of t and the nominal power, respectively. The investigated time period is also indicated by *period*. The yield is calculated here for each month of operation, as well as the whole period. The results are given for black ground and white ground.

In Fig. 11, the amount of monthly yield obtained by PVlib and DBPG model are compared with the observation. Moreover, Fig. 12 gives the total yield values from observation, as well as PVlib and DBPG model estimation. According to Fig. 11a and b, PVlib has a considerable overestimation for both black and white ground conditions during all months. The reason has been explained in details in the pervious part. Moreover, due to the discussion provided in the previous section about power, the error for yield for the ground with white surface is higher. In particular, for the white surface, the error in modeling by PVlib is less in the summer season than the winter. This is because in the summer, the difference between GTI and RTI is much higher and thus the rear-side power output is much lower than that of front-side, which means less error by PVlib modeling. Nonetheless, for all the months and ground conditions, the error remains significant. Based on Fig. 12a and b, there

are 8.47% and 14.01% error in estimation of the total yield for the black and white surfaces, respectively.

Fig. 11a and b also show, according to the accuracy improvement observed in Fig. 9, DBPG model provides a better yield estimation in all the months and for both black and white ground conditions. Fig. 12a shows that PVlib estimates a final yield of $597.4 \frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{kW}_p^{\text{BF,front}}}$ during the whole period ground is black while DBPG model estimates $573.8 \frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{kW}_p^{\text{BF,front}}}$, which is much closer to the observed value ($550.7 \frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{kW}_p^{\text{BF,front}}}$). This results in an error of 4.22%, which is almost a half of PVlib.

In addition, Fig. 12b demonstrates that by application of PVlib and DBPG model, the values of 2122.6 and $1982.4 \frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{kW}_p^{\text{BF,front}}}$ are obtained, respectively for the total yield when ground is white. The observed amount is $1861.8 \frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{kW}_p^{\text{BF,front}}}$. Thus, with DBPG model, the error is more than halved (From 14.01% of PVlib to 6.48%).

It should be noted that although yield has been obtained for all day time during the whole period, DBPG model has been developed using the filtered data (Eq. (6)). The filtered data does not include the periods with the near shadow, which leads to lower accuracy of DBPG model in that time (Overestimation). Excluding the near shadow period form the

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11. Comparing monthly profiles of yield estimated by PVlib and DBPG model with the observed data (a) Black ground; (b) White ground.

Fig. 12. Comparing the yield during the whole period (a) Black ground; (b) White ground.

yield computation we found the values of 414.6 $\frac{kWh}{kW_p^{BF,front}}$ for PVlib, 403.8 $\frac{kWh}{kW_p^{BF,front}}$ for DBPG model, and 401.5 $\frac{kWh}{kW_p^{BF,front}}$ for measurement for the black ground (3.26% and 0.58% error for PVlib and DBPG model). The corresponding values for the white ground are 1870.0 $\frac{kWh}{kW_p^{BF,front}}$ for PVlib, 1761.6 $\frac{kWh}{kW_p^{BF,front}}$ for DBPG model, and 1727.4 $\frac{kWh}{kW_p^{BF,front}}$ for measurement (8.25% and 1.98%). Table 3 summarize these results.

The results showed that the application of DBPG model leads to a significant improvement in power and yield estimation under both high and low albedo conditions. The improvement for the white surface is higher, which is the recommended condition for the ground in a BFPV plant. In particular, if the plant is not affected by near-shadow, the DBPG model can estimate the final yield with an error of less than 2% in the worst case of white soil.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we developed a data-driven physical model to estimate the bifacial PV power output. The model is based on retrieving the so-called Dynamic Bifacial Power Gain (DBPG) from the historical monitoring data under real operating conditions. It was trained and tested on production data of a bifacial PV plant (single axis tracker) owned and managed by Eurac Research, Bolzano, Italy.

The accuracy of the DBPG model was compared with PVlib’s estimation model, which is one of the most widely used approaches and thus taken as a reference. The results have shown that DBPG model outperforms the PVlib one for both black and white ground conditions. PVlib obtains a NRMSE of 2.99% with black soil and 4.59% with white soil. The corresponding values for the DBPG model were 1.14% and 2.02%. According to this significant enhancement in accuracy, much more accurate estimation has been obtained for the total yield by the

DBPG model. It is worth specifying that the considered BFPV system is affected by near shadows at different times of the day, and both the DBPG and PVlib models do not take this effect into account (as this is beyond the scope of the work). If the shaded periods are excluded from yield assessment, in the case of black soil, the error values for yield estimation obtained by PVlib and DBPG models were 3.26% and 0.58%, while, in the white soil case, the corresponding values were 8.25% and 1.98%, respectively. Although the increase in accuracy for both cases is considerable, the error was greater for the white ground (high albedo) because, in this case, errors in the estimation of rear production have a greater impact on the model performance.

The improvement in accuracy of the DBPG model over PVlib can be explained by considering that the latter does not account for degradation, current mismatch due to the “edge effect,” and temporal variability of the bifaciality factor. In contrast, DBPG model was trained on real PV generation data, and thus embeds all these effects. We also showed that an additional source of PVlib errors comes from an incorrect bifaciality factor (required as input from the model). Usually, it is assumed the bifaciality factor as the average value of the modules, but it would be better to consider the lowest measured value. Finally, we emphasize that not only backside production depends on soil albedo, but also backside performance. In the case considered, we found that the performance of the rear-side with white soil is higher than that with black soil. However, it is worth noting that the DBPG model requires a year of historical data for training, whereas PVlib’s approach can be used right from the time of plant operation, simply by using real-time global and rear tilted irradiance and module temperature. Therefore, for performance evaluation of a BFPV system, it is recommended to start by using PVlib’s power estimation model and then, after one year of operation, switch to the more accurate DBPG model.

Like any study, this study is not without limitations, which should be acknowledged to provide a balanced perspective. The first limitation is,

Table 3 Comparing the obtained yield with and without application of the statistical filter.

The ground color	Period	The employed data	Obtained yield ($\frac{kWh}{kW_p^{BF,front}}$)			Error (%)	
			PVlib	DBPG model	Measurement	PVlib	DBPG model
Black	~ 3 months	No filter applied	597.4	573.8	550.7	8.47	4.22
		Statistical filter applied	414.6	403.8	401.5	3.26	0.58
White	~ 17 months	No filter applied	2122.6	1982.4	1861.8	14.01	6.48
		Statistical filter applied	1870.0	1761.6	1727.4	8.25	1.98

as mentioned earlier, DPBG model is data-driven and the historical data is required for developing that (Pvlib not). Another one is DBPG model needs to be trained for each location in which the plant is installed (Pvlib not).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ali Sohani: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marco Pierro:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David Moser:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Cristina Cornaro:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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